

**THE USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA AMONG BAYERO
UNIVERSITY KANO STUDENTS**

ABUBAKAR SHUAIBU ABUBAKAR

CMM/16/MAC/00132

**BEING A RESEARCH PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT
OF MASS COMMUNICATION, BAYERO UNIVERSITY, KANO
IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT FOR THE REQUIREMENT OF THE
AWARD OF BACHELOR OF SCIENCE DEGREE IN
MASS COMMUNICATION**

JULY, 2021

CERTIFICATION

This research project is to certify as having met the requirements of the Department of Mass Communication, Bayero University, Kano for the award of Bachelor of Science degree in Mass Communication.

Date-----

Prof. Gausu Ahmad

(PROJECT SUPERVISOR)

Date-----

Mainasara Y. Kurfi Phd

(HEAD OF DEPARTMENT)

Date-----

Mal. Musa Labaran Makarfi

(LEVEL COORDINATOR)

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my parent for their constant supports towards my academic journey, for they are my powerful beacons who nurtured me up to this level and stand for me through the academic learning process.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am grateful to many people who contributed in various ways in the production of this project work. But all my praises and thanks go first to the Almighty Allah Who predestined this for me. I say all thanks and praises are only for Allah in all circumstances, all glory, honor and adoration be unto His name forever.

I am so grateful to my beloved parents, Alhaji Shuayb Abubakar and Haj. Jameela Sa'ad who thought it was right for me to go for this program. My Uncle Alhaji Basheer who provided the necessary supports to my academic journey, my sister Nusaiba Shuaibu for her words of encouragement and advice. I'm also thankful to my brother Umar Shuayb Abubakar who put in a lot for my work to be where it is. I say may Almighty Allah bless him and grant him the desire of his heart.

Also to be acknowledged is my supervisor prof. Gausu Ahmad who relentlessly under severe pressure still found time to supervise my work. To him I say I am grateful indeed. I also profoundly thank my lecturers who gave me the knowledge for my effective pursuit of Bachelor degree in Mass Communication; Mal. Musa Labaran, Prof. Umaru Pate, Dr. Ashir T. Inuwa, Dr. Sule Ya'u Sule, Dr. Suleiman Yar'adua, Dr. Hadiza Ibrahim, Mal. Binta, Dr. Maryam, Dr. Abubakar Minjibir, Dr. Ibrahim Siraj and the host of other lectures that I couldn't mentioned. I say may Allah rewards them all abundantly.

My profound greeting also goes to my very good friend Sani Lawan Ababiye who was always encouraging me to focus on my studies and read all my books to be prepared and ready ahead of any tests or exams, monitoring my progress with my work, putting in his own quota where necessary. I say may Allah shows him favor in his own work too and also grant his heart desires. Also, to my core friends whom we struggle together, read and share experiences together; Ado

Haruna Ahmadu, Ibrahim Haris Yaqub, Ahmad Mashood, Muhammad Idris, May Allah continues to bless all their endeavours,

To my course mates, knowing you all was the best thing that happened to me. Once again I thank you all for your various contributions. May the Almighty Allah bless you all for me and keep you safe.

ABSTRACT

This study is aimed at finding out the usages of Social Media among Bayero University students with focus on the students in Mass Communication Department. The study will also look at the types of social media platforms used by Mass Communication Students, the extent to which Mass Communication Students use the social media as well as finding out the purposes for which the students use the social media. In the same vein, the study will also find out if there are other gratifications that students derive from the use of social media. The methodology for this study will be survey as it seeks to measure student's usage of social media. Respondents for this research will be purposively sampled from the population of Mass Communication Department. Recommendations based on the later findings of this research will be made at the end of the study.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page -----	1
Certification Page -----	2
Dedication -----	3
Acknowledgement -----	4
Abstract -----	6
Table of Contents-----	7
List of Tables-----	9
CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION -----	10
1.1 Background of the Study-----	10
1.2 Statement of Problems-----	16
1.3 Objectives of the study -----	17
1.4 Research Questions -----	17
1.5 Significant of the Study -----	17
1.6 Scope of the Study -----	18
1.7 Limitation of the Study-----	18
1.8 Population of the Study-----	19
1.9 Research Methodology -----	19
1.10 Operational Definition of Terms-----	19
CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW -----	21
2.1 Conceptual Review -----	21
2.2 Theoretical Review -----	25
2.3 Review of Empirical Studies-----	26

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY -----	34
3.1 Research Design-----	34
3.2 Population of the Study-----	34
3.3 Sampling Technique and Sample Size -----	34
3.4 Research Instrument -----	35
3.5 Validity of the Instrument-----	35
3.6 Data Collection Procedure -----	36
3.7 Data Analysis Procedure -----	36
CHAPTER FOUR: DATA PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION ----	38
4.1 Mode of Questionnaire Administration -----	38
4.2 Analysis of Data Collected-----	38
4.3 Answers to Research Questions -----	39
4.4 Discussion of Findings -----	43
CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, RECOMMENDATIONS---	46
5.1 Summary of Findings -----	46
5.2 Conclusion -----	46
5.3 Recommendations -----	47
5.4 Contributions of the Study to Knowledge-----	48
5.5 Suggestions for further Research -----	49
References-----	50
Appendix -----	56

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Population of the Study -----	34
---	-----------

Table 2: Sampling Technique and Sampling Size -----	35
Table 3: Sex of Respondent -----	38
Table 4: Distribution of Respondent by Age-----	38
Table 5: Distribution of Respondents by Level -----	39
Table 6: Social Media Platforms Used by Mass Communication Students -----	40
Table 7: To What Extent do Mass Communication Students use Social Media? --	41
Table 8: Purpose of Social Media Usage among Mass Communication Students-	41
Table 9: What Other Gratifications Do Mass Communication Students gain from Social Media? -----	42

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Most learning is a social activity which occurs in interaction with others, so it is quite a logical step to integrate social media into learning experiences (Sie et al., 2012). The more social the medium is, the greater the impact communication partners have on each other's behavior (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010).

Social media is a means of interactions among people of different ages in which they create, share and exchange information and ideas in a virtual communities and network. Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) defined social media as “a group of internet – based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web and it allows the creation and exchange of user-generated content and depend on mobile and Web based technologies to create highly interactive platforms through which individuals and communities share, create, discuss and modify user-generated content. Social media is playing an important role in today's online world. The traditional way of meeting each other is long gone and now the world meets at social media websites. It is an instrument on communication that gives information and interacts with its users while giving the information. Social media is a powerful new form of communication and it cuts across rank, profession, age etc. The modern social media surfaced in the earlier 1990s and one of such sites was created in 1994 and was called the “Geocities” which was known for certain characteristics. Facebook is another key example of the social media with over one billion active users as at January 2013. There are different types that have support for educators (blogging, Teacher Tube, Twitter); delivery of content (MIT's Open Courseware, iTunes) and social learning

(Facebook, Google+, blogs, LinkedIn and YouTube). Collaborated projects e.g. Wikipedia, blogs. Micro blog Twitters, Content communities such as YouTube, Flickr, Myspace.com, meet Up, Digg, Daily motion and technologies.

Social media has influenced the educational nationwide in Nigeria and beyond, its introduction has played a significant role in the administration and teaching and learning in both college and university. Social media has changed the traditional way of sharing knowledge and information among students in the higher institutions in Nigeria. The use of social media in knowledge sharing cannot be overestimated as it has helped to enhance access to information and learning with the use of networking in fostering transformation and easing accessibility to information for undergraduate.

A wide variety of characteristics and capabilities have been defined for social media in the literature. However, for the purpose of this study, those features of social media have been considered relevant to knowledge sharing purposes. They have the capabilities that encourage, support, and enable undergraduate students to share their knowledge easily and effectively through different mechanisms. Social connections have become very important and have improved and enhanced accessibility of information and sharing of knowledge tremendously among Nigerian Universities.

Social networking: these sites are fast becoming very popular means of both interpersonal and public communication in Nigeria. Social networking sites are modern interactive communication channels through which people connect to one another, share ideas, experiences, pictures, messages and information of interest. Boyd and Ellison (2007) define social networking sites as:

“Web based services that allow individuals to construct a Public or semipublic profile within a bounded system (2) articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection and (3) view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system.

They are interactive networks which information and communication technology (ICTs) bequeath to the modern society through the instrumentality of the Internet and the telecommunication gadgets. The social media makes it possible to expand the networks and to increase the possibilities for communicating with wider audiences on the globe in knowledge sharing. Over the year, it has become a very useful tools for Nigeria Undergraduates to share knowledge through social media sites with various available gadget which has enhance their carrier achievement in the various higher institution.

The interactive aura of the new media confers an unprecedented popularity on them. Also the ubiquity of the social networking sites within their short period of arrival is unparalleled in the annals of media industry. Awake (2011) buttresses this point by noting that “social networking has become hugely popular. Similarly, it took 38 years for radio to reach 50 million users, 13 years for television to attract the same number and 4 years for the Internet to do so, but it took Facebook 12-month only to gain 200 million users in sharing of knowledge which has become easy and flexible. Social networking sites provide various interactive platforms based on the intentions of their founders. In other words, the social media site by their nature has the capabilities of educating, informing, entertaining and inflaming the audience. Onomo (2012) acknowledged this ability of the media by remarking that social media sites has become “a widespread tool for communication and exchange of ideas, sharing of knowledge in helping individuals and organizations with just causes to reach a phenomenally vast audience that could hitherto not be reached by traditional media.”

Social connections have become very important and have improved the library profession tremendously in Nigeria. According to Suraweera et al (2011) social networking refers to a process of relationship building among a group with a common interest. Social media emerged in Nigeria principally for the purpose of socializing. The Facebook initially was used only for social discussions, however over time, particularly by the turn of the 21st century the grouping of individuals into specific groups emerged.

The World Wide Web enables people to gain access to information, create content and disseminate ideas more efficiently. It optimizes the social networks in which individuals are connected through widening communication channels and lowering costs (Barsky and Purdon 2006). Social networking sites first emerged for Internet users to find long-lost friends and classmates, link with each other and share profiles. An increasing number of individuals have become members of one or more social networking sites leading to soaring membership numbers, largely because these sites are free and easy to use. Lately, these social networking sites have gained a foothold among companies, organizations, and even politicians who want to reach out to their target populations (Read 2006). The wide application of social networking in different contexts appears to have included universities and libraries as well (Boyd and Ellison 2007).

Thus, since inception, social networking sites like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, My Space, Skype, WhatsApp etc. have mesmerized millions of users, many of whom have been made to use these sites as parts of their daily activities. Currently, there is a plethora of social networks with various features meant to suit the different interests of their followers. Some are accessed via computer alone while others can be used with mobile phones. The first identifiable social networking sites was launched in 1997, six degree. It allowed its users to create profiles, list their

friends and in 1998, introduced the friends list where users had the freedom to search for old and new friends. (Zeller 2008).

This however was devoid of the provision for users to upload their profile pictures. Other social networking sites like classmates were founded to aid social interaction among their users but did not have many features like six degrees. Other social networking sites like Friendster and Myspace created virtual community, which would help its members locate old and new ones, shape their personal profile via the Internet and socially idea or opinion under the sun. Two years later, Jack Dorsey Launched Twitter as an online blogging site, while the most recent 2go was founded in 2008 by Michael S. Egan. Therefore, just like radio and television, social networking has spread everywhere in Nigeria and are bound to be sprouting as the new media for are still obscure. In other words, from the analysis carried out by the researcher from the world Internet statistics (2012) it was found that out of the total population of 170,123,740 Nigeria, 5,860,240 numbers of people used Facebook as of 2012. Comparing Burundi and Chad with a similar population of 10,557, 259 and 199 75,648 respectively, the data shows that 37,040 and 36, 940 number of people respectively used Facebook as of 2012. Similarly, Florunso, et al (2010) reviewed that: In Africa, social media networking sites are becoming widely spread than it has ever been before and it appears that people's Perception of this technology is diverse. pp.326).

Furthermore, as a novel phenomenon, it is necessary to examine how UNN students use the new means of communication. This is because student's contribution as youths can make or transform any nation. Essoungou (2010), explain that the new communication technology is one of few ways that young Africans can bypass the inefficiencies in the system that allow the status quo to hold on. It lowers the barriers to entry for everyone to get involved and be heard. A study like this shall help to ascertain whether Students use of the media could be regulated or not. This

is obviously because the disposition of people of a given community could shape the media in existence there, just like a cerebral media scholar, Anim (2007) aptly notes that societies greatly influence the operations and functions of the media that operate within those societies.’‘ The manner in which the social media were used and the role they play in the recent uprising which rocked the middle- East popularly referred to as ‘‘Arab Spring’’ could be deciphered as credence to the above academic observations.

Knowledge has always seen as one of the key strategic resources that can produce sustained long-term competitive advantage. Knowledge is the ability of people and organizations to understand and act effectively. Having knowledge supports to cope with daily routine works and it can also set up everyone to deal with new situations and utilize when needed.

Organizations that need to thrive, compete, and operate in an ever evolving environment, cannot leave the development of knowledge within the organization to chance. The exchange of information and knowledge among employees is a vital part of knowledge management. Actually, the organizations are faced with the challenge how to get people to share their knowledge.

For several decades, the world's best-known forecasters of social change have predicted the emergence of a new economy where brainpower and knowledge, not traditional sources of energy and machine power is the critical resource. However, this future is already here and the knowledge economy has arrived. This evolving era is characterized by rapid change and uncertainty, the increasing importance of knowledge and knowledge management and the popularity of new information technologies that have the potential to radically change the way organization do business.

The single most significant technological development in the last 20 years has been the Internet. The Internet makes it possible for individuals to connect, collaborate and share knowledge,

information, document, photo, video, etc. continuously with anyone in the world. Furthermore, people are able to make use of social media tools in order to increase range and richness of their networks, gather information and nowadays, increasingly organizations are finding ways of integrating social media into their business processes (Gaál et al, 2014).

A concept that has been around for some time, and rose to popularity in the 1990s when Senge (1990) introduced his book the fifth discipline. The art and practice of the learning organization. To this day it is seen as an important concept for organizations. Organizations must learn because the environment around them changes so quickly. Therefore, employees (and thus the whole organization) have to learn to handle these changes

In line of the above, this research work will seek to examine the use of social media by undergraduate students in Bayero University, Kano.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Over the years, social networking sites have metamorphosed from few-user-based sites into phenomena that have become relevant for billions of users. The growth and popularity of social networking sites have generated concerns among school authorities, communication experts and socio-psychological researchers about the benefit and potential risks facing undergraduates, as they engage in online social networking to cater for their social and information needs rather than oral or face-to-face communication.

Social media has influenced the educational sector nationwide in Nigeria and beyond, its introduction has played a significant role in the administration and teaching and learning in both college and university. From researches and past literature, many authors have tried to write about one aspect on the subject of the role of social media in the academic learning process.

Many other work was found in literature that covered the use of social media by undergraduate students. Although, several studies was done on the aspect of social media use by undergraduate students, based on this, this study will fill the gap and aims to survey the use of social media by undergraduate students of Bayero University, Kano.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The specific objectives of this study is to:

1. Identify the types of social media used among BUK students.
2. Determine the extent to which BUK students use social media.
3. Determine the purpose for which BUK students use social media.
4. Find out other gratifications BUK students gains for using social media.

1.4 Research Questions

The following questions will be raised to guide this study:

1. What are the types of social media used among BUK students?
2. To what extent do BUK students use social media?
3. What are the purposes for which BUK students use social media?
4. What other gratifications do BUK students gain for using social media?

1.5 Significant of the Study

It is expected that the output of this research will benefit students and the administration of Bayero University, Kano students as well as show the level of the students' use of social media sites. This study will help them to understand best way to sustain the students' attention on using social media sites. Also this work will be of immense benefit to the field of Library and information sciences

as it will be on addition to existing literature. And shall also add to the available academic literatures on social media.

Also the findings could be used by academic advisers and counselors proffer professional advice to the university authorities on how to regulate the social media usage among undergraduate students of BUK.

Also, the findings of this study would provide facts that will enable the ministry of communication technology to know what arises from students' use of the social media sites. This will help the ministry to know how to control social media usage. Upon successful completion of this research, it shall be very relevant to various people, across Nigeria.

1.6 Scope

The scope of the study was streamlined to both male and female students of mass communication Department, Bayero University, Kano. Department of mass communication is chosen because the researcher is very conversant with its environment.

1.7 Limitation of the Study

The study is being designed to investigate the students' use of social media. Therefore, time will however pose as another limitation of this study especially when viewed against the backdrop of the dynamism of man, which makes it difficult to carry out a behavioral research.

In light of the prevailing economic situation in the country, adequate funds may not be available for the easy completion of this research.

1.8 Population of the Study

Population according to Kerlinger (1981) refers to all members of any well-defined class of either people, events or subject which can be living or non-living. The population of this study is going to be centered only on both male and female students of mass communication department.

1.9 Research Methodology

This study will adopt the survey method of research. The survey method allows for the collection of a large amount of data from a sizeable population in a highly economical way (Saunders *et al.*, 2003: 92).

1.10 Operational Definition of Terms

The following operational definition of terms will be used in this study:

Social media: are computer-mediated tools that allow people to create, share or exchange information, ideas, and pictures/videos in virtual communities and networks. Social media is defined as "a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web, and that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content.

. **Social Networking:** Boyd and Ellison (2007) described social networking websites as systems that allow individuals to: (1) construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, (2) articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection, and (3) view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system.

Uses: to carry out a purpose or action by means of utilizing different social media sites.

Students: A group or selected number of people, who go to school and are learning something. For this study, students are group of people who are learning, such as in college or university. Usually, students will learn from a teacher or a lecturer if at university. They also do much reading.

Internet: This is a worldwide collection of computer networks, a network of networks – sharing digital information via a common set of networking and software protocol (Musciano & Kennedy, 2002:1)

Communication: The process of receiving and transmitting information, ideas and opinions.

Information: the created, stored, processed, retrieved and transmitted set of signals (or symbol). Information in general is anything that has the capacity to reduce the uncertainty.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

Literature review is a description of what have been published on the relating topic by prestigious scholars and researchers. Purpose of review literature is to know the areas in which research have been done relating to the topics, to find out the strength and weakness of the study. Review literature helps in guiding the researcher in better reviewing the objectives of the research need for the study, helps in framing the theoretical frame work of the study, summarizing the current scope and knowledge of the topic under study thus eradicates the possible weakness.

Boateng and Amankwaa (2016) defined social media as the application that allows users to converse and interact with each other. It is an online space that is used by people to connect, share, communicate, establish or maintain connection with others for various purposes. Social media is an online platform which enables people to build social networks or relations with other people who share similar personal or career interests, activities, backgrounds or real-life connections. Social media is therefore the interaction among individuals in which they create and share information and ideas in networks. However, social media relies on many electronic devices like smart phones, tablets, I-pads, I-phones, laptops, and Internet-based technologies for connecting people. Thus, social media can be described as technologies that facilitate social interaction, make collaboration possible, and enable deliberation among people at the global level.

Boyed & Ellison (2007) define social media as Internet-based services that allow individuals to construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection, and traverse their list of connections and those

made by others within the system. According to Ali, Iqbal & Iqbal (2016), social media is the collection of applications such as Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, LinkedIn and YouTube, among others, that link people together as they share information through social networking. As indicated by Junco, Heiberger & Loken (2010), social media is referred to as a collection of Internet websites, services, and practices that support collaboration, community building, participation and sharing. From the above, it can be deduced that social media is the platform that gives individuals the opportunity to interact, using two way communication, such that it allows anyone who has an online account to share their opinions with other social media users.

Social media has become one of the prominent communication tools, particularly in the school community. Talaue, Alsaad, AlRushaidan & AlHagail (2018) emphasize that social media platforms help with access to information and educational-related materials. Considering the aforementioned, many students and instructors are using social media as a teaching and learning tool. More often than not, academic institutions are increasingly using social media platforms, such as Facebook and LinkedIn, to connect with current and potential students and to deliver instructional content (Paul, Baker, & Cochran, 2012) Therefore, social media platforms allow students to interact with one another, their teachers and communities that share in their education and related activities (Pardo 2013). Bearing this in mind, many universities now maintain profiles and groups on social networking sites such as Facebook, WhatsApp and Telegram where students and faculty can interact, share resources and express ideas. *Social Media: uses and Influence on undergraduate studies.*

Conversely, Lenhart, Purcell, Smith & Zickuhr (2010) assert that not all students interact constantly on social media platforms for academic purposes. This suggests that social media platforms are explored by students for different reasons. Junco & Cotton (2012) affirm that time

spent by student on social media is slightly negatively related to time spent studying. In this same manner, Pempek, Yermolayeva & Calvert (2009) declare that most students spend valuable hours daily on social media platforms. Rideout (2012) reveals that young people spend time on social media more than twice the average amount of time spent in school each year. This supports the position of Subrahmanyam & Patricia (2008) who underscore that using social media sites has both negative and positive effects, because there are harmful ways in which the Internet can be used.

Despite the benefits of social media on student learning and achievement with respect to knowledge sharing, Rithika & Sara (2013) underline that even when social media is used for an educational purpose, students incorporate the technology into their lives in a way that may differ from the intentions of the course instructor. Extant literature has provided an array of challenges of social media on students' academic life. O'Keeffe & Kathleen (2011) highlight the negative impacts of social media to include accessing inappropriate content, online harassment, and cyber bullying.

Abdulsalam & Azizah (2012) defined Social media as a variety of technologies that support the social aspects of the Internet as a channel for communication, collaboration, and interaction. Social media is characterized as Web resources that emphasize active participation, connectivity, collaboration, as well as sharing of knowledge and ideas among users. They are used as an educational tool in universities, social media enhances the learning experience by enabling students and teachers to connect and interact in new ways beyond the classroom. Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, WhatsApp and other social sites promote collaboration, knowledge sharing and discussion, and students have embraced them as a means to ask questions, share knowledge and exchange ideas. According to OnlineUniversities.com which carried out a study about the pros

and cons of social media in universities revealed in their findings that 100% of schools studied are using some social media platform or the other, they use it in the classrooms, to enhance school pride, as a professional development tool for teachers, and to reach out to their immediate communities in knowledge sharing and to communicate effectively to prospective students (Pam Dyer on February 4, 2012). Examples of these social media tools are Blogs, Social Network sites like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, WhatsApp, Telegram, Google, Blogger, Word press, Twitter, Friendster, LinkedIn, Digg, Podcasts, YouTube, Multimedia sharing, Interactive website such as Wordle to create materials for learning and assessment, etc.

Social networks are online services, platforms or sites that focus building and reflecting social relations among people, who, for example, share interests and or activities. Social networking sites are websites that allow those who have account with them to communicate with a selected group of friends (Awake, 2011). Social networks comprise a representation of each user (often a profile), his or her social links, and a variety of additional services (Wikipedia, 2011). Most of the social networks are web-based and provide mean for their users to interact via the Internet, such as e-mail and instant messaging; social networks allow activities, events and interact within their individual networks. The inception of social networking sites, to facilitate new forms of computer-mediated social interaction, evolved from early suggestions. Measure and efforts to support social networks via computer-mediated communication (CMC) were made in many early online services; include unset, bulletin board service like America online, prodigy, and CompuServe. Early social networking on the World Wide Web began in the form of generalized online communities such as the glob.com (1995), Geocities (1994) and Tripod.com (1995) (Wikipedia, 2011). Characteristically, many of these early communities focused on bringing people together to interact with one another through chat rooms and encouraged users to share

personal information and ideas via personal web pages by providing easy-to-use publishing tools and free or inexpensive web space. Some network such as classmates.com, Facebook, Twitter etc. took a different approach by simply having people link to each other through e-mail addresses.

New social networking methods were developed at the end of the 1990's and many sites began to design more advanced features for users to find and manage friends. This newer generation of social networks began to blossom with the emergence of six degrees.com in 1997, followed by make out club in 2000, Friendster in 2002 and Myspace in 2003. Social networking sites have become a new means through which individuals can interact and communicate with friends in distance places. As at September, 2011, Facebook had a total number of 800 million active users (Wikipedia, 2011). Today, it is estimated that there are now over 200 active social networks using a wide variety of social networking models.

In Nigeria, the number of social network users is on the high side. According to social bakers, a Facebook statistics site, Nigeria ranks 35th in the world in the number of Facebook users. According to the site, Facebook has an estimate of over 4 million Nigeria users, with the males dominating 65% while the females have a 33% domination.

2.2 Theoretical Review

Uses and Gratification Theory

Uses and Gratification Theory is a theory that takes a more humanistic approach to how we look at media use. The theory came to light in the 1970s and was first propounded by Katz *et al* (1974). The theory maintains that the receivers of media messages selectively choose, attend to, *perceive* and retain the media messages based on their needs. Folarin (2005: 65) added that these needs are related to communication.

This tenet of the uses and gratification theory justifies this study in that social media users would naturally indicate their preferences (if any) for new media platforms and this will come as a result of their perceived gratification and beliefs which they get from using the social media. Wimmer & Dominick (2000: 385) viewed these gratifications and beliefs as the motivating factors, which underlie consumer's use of media contents. McQuail (2005: 569) added that the theory seeks to explain the uses of media and the satisfaction derived from this in terms of the motives and self-perceived needs of audience members.

Folarin (2005) views this theory by putting forward the fundamental question: "who uses which contents from which media under which conditions and for what reasons?" No wonder, Meyrowitz (2002: 101) noted that the users take an active part in the communication process and are goal oriented in their media use.

From the foregoing, it has become evident that the uses and gratification theory has been able to provide a solid foundation on which this study is built. It points specifically at the invaluable place of social media users measuring how social networking sites are faring on the internet. These tenets of uses and gratification theory will help in successfully reaffirming the existing structures of the internet from which the social media platforms get to the users.

2.3 Review of Empirical Studies

The interactive nature of social media such as Twitter, Facebook, WhatsApp, Telegram, and YouTube and so on has further popularized the tools among undergraduates across the world as it allows them to re-create contents, connect, upload and share information. Social media is seen as an interactive web-based platform in which individuals, groups and communities discuss, share, connect, co-create and disseminate relevant information based on common goal

(Kietzmann, Hermkens, McCarthy and Silvestre, 2011:241). This technology has impacted students-societies as they have changed the way they communicate and relate with one another through online channels and the conduct of their daily activities (Tanakinjal, Sondoh, Andrias and Ibrahim, 2012).

Akakandelwa and Walubita (2018:1) noted that WhatsApp was the commonly used social media tools among the students and that they engage actively on these tools between 31 to 60 minutes on daily basis. Also, the respondents indicated that they used the social networking sites tools more for social life than for academic activities. In contrast, Hussain (2012) noted that majority of the students 90% acknowledged that they preferred using Facebook to other social media tools like Twitter, LinkedIn, and Web-Blog etcetera. The study also affirmed that 82% of the respondents utilize Facebook on daily basis followed by Google Group 74% and Twitter 71%, while only 2% used the Web-Blog on monthly basis. Asemah, Okpanachi and Edegoh (2013) found in their study on social media and undergraduates' academic performance in North-Central Nigeria. The study revealed that undergraduates' exposure to social networking sites has negative effects on them particularly their academic performance. This was in agreement with study by Lahiry, Choudhury, Chatterjeen and Hazra (2019) who noted that almost two-thirds 60.87% of the respondents agreed that social networking sites have positively enhanced their academic performance. Boahene, Fang and Sampong (2019:1) avowed that the use of social media for educational activities positively associated to academic performance. The study further discovered that social media usage can negatively influence students' academic performance.

Kolan and Dzanza (2018) discovered that about 50.3% of the Ghanaian students spent over two hours on social media daily and that 82.5% noted that they majorly use the social media tools for downloading videos, pictures and chatting while 32% of the respondents mostly use the

social media tools for academic purposes. Fatokun (2019:9) noted that 60.8% of the undergraduate students engage in social media tools mostly for educational associated activities while 52.9% of the respondents attested that social media tools have assisted in boosting their cumulative grade point average (CGPA). In supporting the above, Mowafy (2018:45) noted that large proportion 47.4% of the undergraduate students at Nile University, Egypt disagree that social media have negative influence on their GPA. Also, the respondents stipulated that they spend more time using social media daily with mean score of $m=6.71$ and $SD=5.15$, this was further corroborated by (Kolan and Dzanza, 2018) above.

Apuke (2016) found that undergraduate students who spend most of their time on social networking sites are liable to perform awfully in their academic purposes than those who did not. This was in tandem with findings by Talaue, AISaad, AIRushaidan, AIHugail and AIFahhad (2018:34) who found that the time spend engaging on social media have negative influence on students' academic performance. Ghareb and Sharif (2015, 818) found that undergraduate students use more of Facebook on daily basis with average of 1-3 hour and this negatively affects their academic performance. Observing the major obstacles, challenges or constraints encountered by undergraduates on the use of social medial, Wickramanayake and Jika (2018:21) noted that erratic power generated; cost of internet connectivity and low bandwidth in internet connection as well as issues associated with privacy and security were noticed as some constraints to students' social media usage. This agreed with study by Hussain (2012:644) who reported the major problems faced by students on social media use to be unstable electricity 93%; low internet bandwidth 77%; poor time management 89% particularly during session; lack of infrastructure 72%. Privacy and security issues, ergonomics, blurred vision as well as cyber bullying were also identified as the constraints to social media use.

Fatokun (2019) further identified habit, health issues, distraction as well as poor time management as some of the barriers to the use of social media tools among undergraduate students in Nigeria. Abbas, Aman, Nurunnabi and Bano (2019) highlighted the constrains to the use of social networking sites among students in Pakistan which include poor of critical thinking; time wasting; slow writing skills; leads to laziness as well as health problems.

However, in international Journal of Education and Development Using Information and Communication Technology (IJEDICT), 2019, Vol. 15, Issue 3, pp. 53-62. In a Study Conducted by Subair S. Tayo Solomon Temitope Adebola and Deborah Oreoluwa Yahya, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-ife, Nigeria.

During this study, they use Survey method to guide the study. This method was considered suitable as it enabled the researchers to investigate the already existing situation and acquire first-hand information from the respondents in order to interpret, discuss and report situations as they exist. The population for the study comprised all undergraduate students at Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. The random sampling technique was used to select five faculties. From each faculty, 170 undergraduates were selected using convenience sampling technique. The sample for the study comprised 850 students. A self-designed and validated instrument titled “Social Media Usage and Influence Questionnaire (SMUI-Q)” was used to elicit information from the respondents. The research instrument was subjected to both face and construct validity measures for consistency. The reliability of the instrument was ensured at 0.86 reliability coefficient. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentages.

Table: Social
Media Platforms
Used by
Undergraduate
Students

S/N	Social Media	Frequency	Percentage
1.	WhatsApp	829	97%
2.	Facebook	724	85%
3.	Instagram	552	65%
4.	YouTube	531	62%
5.	Twitter	241	25%
6.	LinkedIn	174	21%
7.	Google Plus	128	15%
8.	Snap chat	84	10%
9.	Skype	63	7%

Source: Field Survey, 2019

As can be seen in the Table above, the four social media platforms mostly used by students at Obafemi Awolowo University are WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube. *IJEDICT* The data in also affirmed that most of the undergraduate students use social media platforms

mainly for socialization, information, and academic purposes. This is in keeping with the trend for youths to engage in social media usage largely to socialize with friends and families. This perhaps explains the priority given to the purpose of using social media.

Emanating from the study are findings that the social media platforms mostly used by the undergraduate students are WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram and YouTube. This corroborates the findings of Wiley & Sisson (2006) who stated that more than 90% of tertiary school students use social platforms. The findings from the study also support Kaya & Bicen (2016) who disclosed that Facebook and WhatsApp were mostly used by students. Hashem & El-Badawy (2015) noted that the social media types used by students include Snap chat, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and YouTube. As such, the study results are validated. Also, findings from the study indicate that undergraduate students spend an average of 2 to 3 hours daily on social media platforms

In the same way, findings from the study indicate that undergraduates used social media platforms mainly for socialization, information, and academic purposes. The reason for this is not far from the priority the undergraduates placed on the purposes of using social media platforms. This perhaps explains the extent of influence the social media platforms has on their studies. The findings support the study of Talaue, Alsaad, AlRushaidan & AlHagail (2018) who noted that the purposes of social media platforms usage by students included getting information for educational and entertainment purposes. From the results, it can be deduced that the undergraduate students use social media platforms for socialization more than they do for academic purposes. This finding upholds that in the study by Oye (2012), who observed that social media platforms are mainly used by students for socializing activities rather than academic purposes. In the same vein, Owusu-Acheaw & Larson (2015) revealed that students mainly used

Social media sites to chat rather than for academic purposes. Students tend to connect with friends for chatting purpose rather than to engage in conversation to seek academic knowledge. Furthermore, findings from the study reveal that Internet addiction and distraction are the major influences of social media on undergraduate studies. The result is not far from the claims of some of the participants' habit of spending hours daily on social media with the resultant effect of postponing their academic tasks to spend time on the social media platforms, usually to while away time. Support for this finding can be seen in the study by Ndaku (2013) which showed that students spend much of their study time on social media which has diverted their attention from attaining educational objectives. Further, Rideout (2012) has shown that students spend time on social media platforms more than twice the average amount of time spent in school each year. This view is however rejected by Onyeka, Sajoh & Bulus (2013) who acknowledged that social media sites not only re-engage learners with their studies but also enhance their academic performance.

On another study conducted by Ogedengbe, Osebhajimende Esther Mrs and Quadri, Ganiyu Oluwaseyi Mr, "The use of social Media by Undergraduates in South-West Nigeria: A comparative Study" 2020, Library Philosophy and practice (e-journal). 3860.

The target population consisted of undergraduates of Olabisi Onabanjo University, and Bowen University, Iwo. There were ten (10) faculties offering undergraduate program at Olabisi Onabanjo University with a population of eleven thousand three hundred and sixty-one (11,361) undergraduates, while only seven (7) faculties offering undergraduate program at Bowen University with a population of three thousand nine hundred and thirty (3930) undergraduates. This gave a total of fifteen thousand two hundred and ninety-one (15,291).

The first research question which examined the frequency of use of social media tools by undergraduates in both universities revealed that WhatsApp, Facebook, YouTube was highly utilized and Twitter being the most frequently used social media tools for academic related work, interaction, sharing of information on daily basis. This is an indication that the use of social media tools has been widely embraced by undergraduates in these universities. The above findings agreed with earlier studies by Akakandelwa and Walubita (2018), Kolan and Dzanza (2018) and Hussain (2012) who reported that WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Web-Blog, Google Group were all frequently used on daily basis for education activities.

The second research question also reported in this study that respondents from both universities were faced with different challenges in the use of social media especially for their academic activities, the following were some of the identified hiccups Cyber-bullying, lack of privacy, time wasting, addiction problem as well as being distracted to the use of social media. This was in consonance with the study by Wickramanayake and Jika (2018) who reported that that erratic power generated, cost of internet connectivity and low bandwidth in internet connection as well as issues associated with privacy and security were noticed as some constraints to students' social media usage. Also, Hussain (2012) reported that unstable electricity, poor time management, lack of infrastructure, privacy and security issues, ergonomics, blurred vision as well as cyber bullying were identified as the constraints to social media usage by undergraduate students in the Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHOD

3.1 Research Design

This study will adopt the survey method of research. The survey method allows for the collection of a large amount of data from a sizeable population in a highly economical way (Saunders *et al*, 2003: 92).

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of this study covered both male and female Mass Communication students of Bayero University, Kano.

Table 3.2:

SN	DEPARTMET	LOCATION	Student Population
1	Mass Communication	BUK	591

3.3 Sampling Technique and Sample Size

The sample for this study is drawn from five hundred and ninety one students (591), which represent the total population of all Mass Communication students of Bayero, University, Kano. In order to arrive at a sample size, the accidental sampling technique was used in selecting the sample. Accidental sampling procedure allows the researcher to administer the research tool to the respondents on the basis of first come first served. Hence the researcher intends to use a

total of two hundred (200) undergraduate Mass Communication students of Bayero, University for this study.

This is shown in the Table 3.3:

SN	DEPARTMENT	LOCATION	Sampling size
1	Mass Communication	BUK	200

3.4 Research Instrument

The research instrument which will be employed by the researcher in this study is the questionnaire, which will be administered to both male and female students in Mass Communication Department. The questionnaire will comprise of both open ended and close ended questions which will be divided into two sections – Sections A and B. Section A, will consist of questions with relevance to the framework of this study were asked. While section B, will be bothering on the respondents’ bio-data.

The open-ended questions will give the respondents the freedom to air their opinion freely on other gratifications the get from the social media, while the close ended questions allowed the respondents to express their feelings in a scaled form.

3.5 Validity of the Instrument

The research instrument will be validated by the research supervisor who will also vet the items in the instrument critically. In addition, the items contained in the instrument will be

coherent, sequential, comprehensive, and therefore capable of testing what the study is set out to achieve.

Similarly, the instrument will also be valid because data from the study will not only come from one category of respondents but from various level of students.

Moreover, the instrument will not only be streamlined to one variable but will take cognizance of other variables such as sex, age, status, etc.

3.6 Data Collection Procedure

Apart from reviewing related literatures, the researcher will administer the questionnaire to both male and female students in Mass Communication Department, Bayero University, Kano.

The researcher will also administer the questionnaire on a person-to-person basis. In effect, the completed questionnaire will be collected on the spot after administration. This is to ensure that the total numbers of questionnaire administered are the same or nearly the same with the number retrieved. Moreover, the researcher will be present to answer any oral questions from the respondents and to give guidance on how the questionnaire should be filled.

3.7 Data Analysis Procedure

In this study, data collected will be analyzed using the simple percentages analysis and will be presented with the help of tables and graphs. The simple percentage analysis is to enable the researcher to fully explore and explain the data collected and collated from the questionnaire without the use of complex mathematical models, which are generally not easy to comprehend.

The formula for the simple percentage is shown below:

$$\text{Percentage} = \frac{\text{Actual response}}{\text{Total sample size}} \times 100$$

The data collected will be measured in terms of the frequency and percentage distribution of the different categories of variables displayed in the table.

On the other hand, the tables and graphs will provide a visual aid for the collated data. No doubt, the use of graphs will also make a quick lasting and accurate impression of the significant facts and also make the points clearer, (Okoro, 2001: 81).

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

4.1 Mode of Questionnaire Administration

In this work, 200 hundred copies of questionnaire were administered on the corresponding number of respondents chosen from Mass Communication Students, Bayero University, Kano.

The copies were administered, analyzed and discussed. Out of the two hundred copies that were administered, only 193 were returned, 96 respondents representing 49% were males, and 97 respondents representing 51% were females.

4.2 Analysis of Data Collected

Table 4.1: SEX OF RESPONDENT

Gender	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Male	96	49%
Female	97	51%
Total	193	100%

From the above table, female respondents were represented by 97 (51%) while the male respondents were represented by 96 (49%).

Table 4.2: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENT BY AGE

AGE	FREQUENCY	P ERCENTAGE
16-20	44	22.5%
21-25	102	52.5%
26-30	34	17.5%

30 and above	13	7.5%
Total	193	100.0%

From the above table, it shows the distribution of respondents by age. It can be seen that 102 (52.6%) of the respondents were between the ages of 21 – 25, while 44(22.8%) were between 16- 20, 26-30 age respondents constituted 34 (17.5%) while only 13 (7.1%) of the respondents were between the age of 30 and above.

Table 4.3: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENT BY LEVEL

LEVEL	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
100	41	21%
200	48	25%
300	49	25.5%
400	55	28.5%
Total	193	100.0%

From above table, indicates that 55 (28.5%), 49 (25.5%), 48 (25%), and 41 (21%) were from 400 level, 300 level, 200 level, and 100 level respectively.

4.3 Answers to Research Questions

Research Question 1: what are the types of social media students frequently use?

To answer this research question, data were group into two and analyzed using frequency counts and percentages as shown in the table below:

Table 4:4: Social Media Platforms Used by Mass Communication Students

S/N	SOCIAL MEDIA	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1.	Facebook	163	81.5%
2.	WhatsApp	185	92.5%
3.	Instagram	121	60.5%
4.	You Tube	128	64%
5.	Twitter	83	41.5%
6.	Telegram	54	27%
7.	Snap chat	72	36%
8.	Google+	99	49.5%
9.	LinkedIn	15	7.5%
10.	Skype	9	4.5%

Sources: Field Survey, 2021.

From table 4.4 above, it was revealed that WhatsApp was the most used social networking sites by students with 185 (95.6%), followed by Facebook 163 (89.7%), YouTube 128 (74.8%), Instagram, 121 (69.7%).

Research Question 2: To what extent do mass communication students use social media?

Extent to which do Mass Communication Students Use Social Media

Table 4:5

S/N	DURATION	FREQUENCY	PENTAGERCE
1.	Daily	152	78%
2.	Weekly	7	3.5%
3.	1-3 Hours	16	8.5%
4.	3-5 Hours	14	7.5%
5.	Others: Always Online	4	2.5%
	TOTAL	193	100%

Sources: Field Survey, 2021.

Table 4:5 shows the results on the extent to which Mass Communication students spent their time on social media. Most of the Mass communication students use the social media on the daily basis which is represented by 152 students' equivalent to 78%. Other students indicated that they spent an average of 1-3 hours daily on social media platform.

Research Question 3: What are the purposes for which mass communication students use social media?

Table 4:6 Purpose of social media usage among Mass Communication students

S/N	PURPOSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGES
1.	News Generation	36	18%
2.	Academic Purpose	40	22%

3.	Social Interaction	70	35%
4	Entertainment	26	14%
5	Others	21	11%
	TOTAL	193	100%

Sources: Field Survey, 2021.

The data in Table 6 affirmed that most of the undergraduate students use social media platforms mainly for social, interaction, and academic purposes. This is in keeping with the trend for youths to engage in social media usage largely to socialize with friends and families. This perhaps explains the priority given to the purpose of using social media.

Research Question 4: What other gratifications do Mass Communication Students gain from social media?

Table 4.7

S/N	STATEMENT	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
	Online Business/Advert	93	47.5%
	Video Call	26	14%
	Increase Exposure	30	15%
	Recreation	31	16%
	Reduce Burdensome	13	7.5%
	TOTAL	193	100%

Sources: Field Survey, 2021.

Responses in table 7 show other gratification and benefits that Mass Communication students derive from the use of social media is engaging themselves in an online business which is represented by 47.5% of the students. 16% use the social media that satisfy their needs as a form of recreation.

15% use the social media to increase their exposure about what is happening in the real world. 14% use social media platforms for video call. While on 7% use it to reduce burdensome.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

Findings from this study showed that; the most widely social media platforms used by Mass Communication students in Bayero University, Kano are WhatsApp, Facebook, YouTube, followed by Instagram and then Google plus. This corroborates the findings of Wiley & Sisson (2006) who stated that more than 90% of tertiary school students use social platforms. The findings from the study also support Kaya & Bicen (2016) who disclosed that Facebook and WhatsApp were mostly used by students. Hashem & El-Badawy (2015) noted that the social media types used by students include Snap chat, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and YouTube. As such, the study results are validated. Also, findings from the study indicate that Mass Communication students spend their time on social media platforms daily and an average of 1 to 3 hours daily on social media platforms. This may explain the extent of Internet addiction among undergraduates. The finding is in keeping with the study by Talaue, Alsaad, AlRushaidan & AlHagail (2018) which revealed that students spend on average 1 to 3 hours per day on social media. Similarly, Hashem & El-Badawy (2015) indicated that 50% of students spend 1 to 3 hours studying a day and 33% spent that same amount of time on social media per day.

Emanating from the findings of this study also indicate that students use social media largely for effective social interaction, academic purposes and then news generation. The reason for this is not far from the priority the undergraduates placed on the purposes of using social media platforms. This perhaps explains the extent of influence the social media platforms has on their studies. The findings support the study of Talaue, Alsaad, AlRushaidan & AlHagail (2018) who noted that the purposes of social media platforms usage by students included getting

information for educational and entertainment purposes. From the results, it can be deduced that the mass communication students use social media platforms for socialization more than they do for academic purposes. Media platforms are mainly used by students for socializing activities rather than academic purposes. In the same vein, Owusu-Acheaw & Larson (2015) revealed that students mainly used social media sites to chat rather than for academic purposes. Students tend to connect with friends for chatting purpose rather than to engage in conversation to seek academic knowledge.

Other gratification driven from the use of social media indicated by the students include: business and adverts, video call, professional growth, driving pleasure, serving as a form of recreation, inspiration, increase exposure, reducing burdensome and as well serve as a form of inspiration.

Findings from this study showed that; students' use of social media is for assignment ranked highest followed by research and for self-satisfaction purposes. These findings is in line with findings of Awake (2011) stated that social networks are online networks or sites that focus on building social relations among people, who, for example shares interest or activities. This is also in consonant with the work of Gross (2004) he noted that "students use social networking sites not only for leisure and personal socialization but also as a platform for more meaningful and serious deliberations, and students are using social networking for making friends, sharing links, online learning, finding jobs to accomplish their economic, educational, political and social being". This is also supported by the study of Minocha, (2009), he stated that social media enhances a student's sense of community, sharing and collaboration, brings an additional responsibility and workload, which some students find inflexible and rather "forced". This technology uses web cams or voice-only Software to hold virtual seminars online. This is extremely useful for collaborations

where, the Partners live in different parts of the globe. Through the use of social media, students are able to express themselves, communicate and collect profiles that highlight their talent and experience. Also, Konetes and McKeague in 2011, came up with certain revelations about the uses of the social media especially, Facebook, The researchers reported that, students are using Facebook and other channels to develop their identities, beliefs and stances on various issues such as politics, religion, economy and work, as well as to pioneer and develop intimate relationships. This findings is also in line with the findings of Pam Dyer (2012) on social media blogs used by students, such as Facebook, twitter, Instagram, YouTube, BBM, WhatsApp.

In another findings, Harson (2009) stresses that: Other social networking websites have tight, niche focuses, and cater for specific groups of people. Social networking websites can revolve around sports, dating, culture, hobbies, ethnicity, education, romance, entrepreneurship and more. In addition, social network can be categorized based on ownership of the websites and they are founded to achieve some specific goals which are determined by the owners.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusion, recommendations, contributions of the study to knowledge and suggestions for further research.

5.1 Summary of Findings

- i. Findings on demographic characteristics shows that most of the respondent were females which is represented by 97 (51%) while males' respondents were represented by 96 (49%). It also shows that distribution of respondents by age can be seen that 102 (52.5%) of the respondents were between the ages of 21 – 25, while 44 (22.5%) were between 16- 20, 26- 30 age respondents constituted 34 (17.5%) while only 13 (7.5%) of the respondents were between the age of 30 and above.
- ii. Mass Communication Students used WhatsApp, Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, Google plus and Twitter the most.
- iii. Students used social media for social interaction and for entertainment purposes.
- iv. Students used social medial for academic purposes and news generation.
- v. Other gratifications that Mass Communication students drive from the use of social media include online business and advertisements, increase exposure, video call, reduce boring moment and also use it as a form of recreation.

5.2 Conclusion

Based on the findings from the study, it was discovered that Mass Communication students frequently use social media for one form of activity or the other. Also, the level of awareness of all respondents indicated that they are aware of social media tools around them and the social

media tools they use most are the social network sites followed by YouTube. Consequently, purposes of using social media varies among all respondents but the core purpose of using these are for keeping in touch with friends and it also go a long way in helping undergraduate students in carrying out their various research for academic purposes.

In conclusion, the results obtained from this study have shown that a reasonable number of Mass Communication students use the social media sites. Therefore, The popularity of the social media usage by undergraduate students of Bayero University, Kano under Mass Communication Department and the benefits it has on the student –users have been confirmed from the findings of this study. There are also various purposes for which the students use the social media sites to achieve their set up goals have also been investigated.

5.2 Recommendations

No doubt, a research involves an investigation geared towards increasing knowledge and providing ideas to solve problems. From this fact, coupled with an enthusiastic desire to ensure confirmatory evidence on this study, particularly in the aspect of achieving a greater feeling of certainty for likely purpose of making generalization in the future, the researcher, therefore, deem it fit and necessary to make useful recommendations.

Based on the findings drawn from this study, the researcher has made the following recommendations:

1. Regulation of the use of Mobile Phones during lectures: Since the students access the various social media sites through their mobile phones, it is advisable that Bayero University Governing councils and the University senate has to enact laws, making

students' use of phones during lectures an offence which shall attract drastic punitive measures for the culprits.

2. Also, tertiary institutions, especially the area under study, should organize a seminar to enlighten the students on the negative aspect of using social media sites as medium of interaction. This can be done by exposing students to the importance of face to face communication in the creation of real communication or message sharing.
3. Provision of laws on the content of social media: the study also recommended that there has to be laws guiding the students' use of the social networking sites and what they disseminate through the media.
4. The federal ministry of information and the National Orientation Agency should draft regulatory measures to control the workings of social media sites that are accessible by Nigeria students.
5. Students should moderate the use of sites to avoid addiction and create a balance between their offline and online lives while using the sites.

5.4 Contributions of the Study to Knowledge

Current research contributes some useful insights to the existing literature on use of Social media by students' for self-development. Another contribution of this study is adjusting Social Media usage motivations by applying it in to a new cultural context. Apart from that, the present study compares the phenomenon in an emerging and developed economy and explores the similarities and differences in the Motivations and Usage Patterns of Social media by students.

Social media plays a significant role in academic cycle especially among students.

From the research finding, the social media sites have been seen as a source of direct response to the need to offering adequate information, Communication, disseminate, discussing

and mobilizing vast quality of information. It is important at this point to encourage the federal Ministry of information and the National Orientation Agency to address the various Dangers that are associated with social networking and that will go a long way to enhancing the services offered by the social media.

5.5 Suggestions for Further Research

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher suggests that further studies should be undertaken in the following areas;

- i. This study could be replicated using some other variables of the students not explored in this study. Examples are: use of social media among part time students. This is being suggested because this present study concentrated only on undergraduate students.
- ii. This present study could also be replicated using other forms of institution such as the polytechnic or colleges of education in Nigeria.
- iii. This present study could also be replicated focusing on the attitude of students towards the use of social medial among polytechnic and colleges of education in Kano State and part-time students.

REFERENCES

- Abbas, J., Aman, J., Nurunnabi, M. and Bano, S. (2019). The impact of social media on learning behavior for sustainable education: evidence of students from selected Universities in Pakistan. *Sustainability* 11(6): 1-23.
- Abdulsalam K. A., & Azizah, A. R. (2013): Facebook in Higher Education: Students' Use and Perceptions, *Advances in information Sciences and Service Sciences (AISS) Volume5*, Number15, October 2013
- Akakandelwa, A. and Walubita, G. (2018). Students' social media use and its perceived impact on their social life: a case study of the University of Zambia. *The International Journal of Multi-Disciplinary Research* 1-15.
- Anim, E. (2007). The influence of geo-political affiliations on newspapers' coverage of national issues. In *international Journal of Communication: an interdisciplinary Journal of communication*. (2). P. 23 -27.
- Apuke, D.O. (2016). The influence of social media on academic performance of undergraduate students of Taraba State University, Jalingo, Nigeria. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences* 6(19): 63-72.
- Asemah, E.S., Okpanachi, R.A. and Edegoh, L.O.N. (2013). Influence of social media on the academic performance of the undergraduate students of Kogi State University, Anyigba Nigeria. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences* 3(12): 90-96.
- Awake, (2011, July). *What Should I know social networking?* Part 1, pp. 24.25.

Barsky P. N and Purdon A. V (2006) the impact of Social Networking on organizations. The Electronic Library, 27, 6, 906-918.

Boahene, K.O., Fang, J. and Sampong, F. (2019). Social media usage and tertiary students' academic performance: examining the influence of academic self-efficacy and innovation characteristics. *Sustainability* 11(1): 1-17.

Boyd, D.M., Ellison B.N. (2007), Social Networking Sites: definition of history and scholarship: *Journal of computer –mediated Communication*, 13(1) (2007), pp. 210-230.

Fatokun, K.V. (2019). Effect of social media on undergraduate students' achievement and interest in chemistry in the Northcentral geo-political zone of Nigeria. *International Journal of Science and Technology Educational Research* 10(2): 9-15.

Folarin, B. (2005). *Theories of Mass Communication: An Introductory Text* (3rd edi.). Ibadan: Bakinfo Publications.

Folorunso, O., Vincent, R.O., Adekoya, A.F & Adewale, O.O. (2010). Diffusion of innovation in social networking sites among university students. In *International Journal of Computer Science and security (IJCSS)*, (4)3, pp.361-372.

Egbule, J.F. (1999) *Format for Writing a Research Report*. Agbor: Kmensuo.

Essoungou, A.M. (2011). Nigeria's April elections set new records in use of social media. Retrieved from: <http://nigeriansabroadlive.com/nigerias-april-of-social-media/>. Accessed on December 17, 2011

Gaál F. Luyt, B., Ally, Y., Low, N.H., Ismail, N.B., (2010). Librarian Perception of Wikipedia: Threats or Opportunities for Librarianship? *Library*, 1, 60, 57-64.

Retrieved: May 15, 2010

Ghareb, M.I. and Sharif, H.O. (2015). Facebook effect on academic performance and social life for undergraduate students of university of human developments. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary and Current Research*, 3(4): 811-820.

Halloran, J. D. (2000). "Aspects of Western Social Science Research Models and their (Appropriateness) to Mass Communication Research in the Third World", in Uche, L. U. (Ed.) *North-South Information Culture: Trends in Global Communication and Research Paradigms*. Ikeja: Longman Nig. Plc.

Hashem, Y. & El-Badawy, T. A. 2015. "The impact of social media on the academic development of school". *International Journal of Business Administration*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 46-52.

Hussain, I. (2012). A study to evaluate the social media trends among university students. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 64: 639-645.

Junco, R., Heiberger, G. & Loken, E. 2010. "The effect of Twitter on college students' engagement and grades". *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, pp. 1-14.

Katz, E., Blumler, J.G and Gurevitch, M. (1994) "Utilization of Mass Communication by the Individual", in Blumberg & E. Katz (eds) *The Uses of Mass Communication*. Beverly Hills, California: Sage.

Kaplan Andreas, M., Haenlein Michael, (2010), Users of the world. Unite: The Challenges of Opportunities of social media *Business Horizons*, vol. 53 Issue I (page 67).

Kaya, T. & Bicen, H. 2016. "The effects of social media on students' behaviors; Facebook as a case study". *Computers in Human Behavior*, vol. 59, pp. 374-79

Kerlinger, F. N (1981). *Foundations of Behavioral Science*. Holt, Rinehart and Winston. Inc.

Kietzmann, J.A., Hermkens, K., McCarthy, I.P. and Silvestre, B.S. (2011). Social media? Get serious! Understanding the function building blocks of social media. *Business Horizons* 54: 241-251.

Kolan, B.J. and Dzanza, P.E. (2018). Effect of social media on academic performance of students in Ghanaian universities: a case study of University of Ghana, Legon. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal). 1637.

Lenhart, A., Purcell, K., Smith, A., & Zickuhr, K. 2010. "Social media & mobile internet use among teens and young adults". *Pew Internet and American Life Project*, pp. 1-37.

McQuail, D. (2005) *McQuail's Mass Communication Theory*. (5th ed). London: Sage

Meyrowitz, J. (2002) "Media and Behaviour: a missing link" in McQuail D. (Ed), *McQuail's Reader in Mass Communication Theory*. London: Sage

Mowafy, G. (2018). The effects of social media on the academic performance of Nile University Students. Unpublished dissertation (Masters). Department of International and Comparative Education, the American University.

Ogedengbe, O. Esther & Quadri, G. Oluwaseyi, (2020) “The use of social Media by Undergraduates in South-West Nigeria: A comparative Study” *Library Philosophy and practice* (e-journal). 3860.

Okoro, N. (2001) *Mass Communication Research: Issues and Methodologies*. Nsukka: AP Express.

Onyeka, N. C., Sajoh, D. I. & Bulus, L. D. 2013. “The effect of social networking sites usage on the studies of Nigerian students”. *The International Journal of Engineering and Science*, vol. 2, no. 7, pp. 39-46.

Pempek, T. A., Yermolayeva, Y. A., & Calvert, S. L. 2009. “College students’ social networking experiences on Facebook”. *Journal of Applied Development Psychology*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 227-238.

Senge, P. M. (1990). *The fifth discipline: the art and practice of the learning organizations*. New York: Doubleday Currency.

Sie, R. L. L., Berlanga, A. J., Rajagopal, K., Pannekeet, K., Drachsler, H., Fazeli, S., & Sloep, P. B. (2012). *Social tools for networked learning: Current and future research directions*. Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Networked Learning 2012, Edited by: Hodgson V, Jones C, de Laat M, McConnell D, Rydberg T & Sloep P. 56 – 68.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. (2003) *Research Methods for Business Students*. (3rd ed). England: Prentice – Hall.

Suraweera, S. N., et al (2011). *Value of social networking in libraries and information organizations in Asia and Oceania*. World Library and Information Congress, 76th IFLA General Conference and Assembly. 10-15 August 2010, Gothenburg, Sweden.

Tejumaiye, J. A. (2003). *Mass Communication Research: An Introduction*. Lagos: Scepter Print Ltd.

Wickramanayake, L. Jika, S.M. (2018). Social media use by undergraduate students of education in Nigeria: a survey. *The Electronic Library* 36(1): 21-37.

Wimmer, R.D. & Dominick J.R. (2000) *Mass Media Research: An Introduction*. (6th edition). California: Wadsworth.

Online Sources

Onomo, A.A. (2012, January 15). People power. 15 social media. *The Guardian*, pp. 38.

Read S. K. (2006) Knowledge sharing in wiki communities: an empirical study. *Online Information Review*, 5, 35, 799 – 820. Retrieved: May 15, 2012, from emerald insight, Available at: <http://www.emeraldinsight.com/journals.htm?articleid=1953777>

Wikipedia. List of social networking websites. Retrieved February 12, 2012 www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki/social-networking-service...

Zeller, Bill (September 2008). Popular Websites Vulnerable to Cross-Site Request forgery Attacks. Retrieved April 27, 2008. From World Wide Web: <http://www.freedom.totinker>

Department of Mass Communication,

Faculty of Communication,

-----,

-----.

June -----.

Dear Respondent,

REQUEST FOR COMPLETION OF QUESTIONNAIRE

I am ----- student of the Department of Mass Communication, ----- . I am conducting a research on the topic:

THE USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA AMONG BAYERO UNIVERSITY, KANO STUDENTS

The research is an academic study in fulfillment of the requirements for the award of a ----- Degree of -----s in Mass Communication.

I shall be grateful if you can complete the attached questionnaire for me. Your anonymity is guaranteed as the information will be treated in utmost confidentiality.

Thanks.

(Researcher

QUESTIONNAIRE

SECTION (A)

Please tick [] in the box provided against your choice of answer.

1) The types of social media you frequently use:

Do you use?	YES	NO
1. Facebook	[]	[]
2. WhatsApp	[]	[]
3. Instagram	[]	[]
4. YouTube	[]	[]
5. Twitter	[]	[]
6. Telegram	[]	[]
7. Snap chat	[]	[]
8. Google+	[]	[]
9. LinkedIn	[]	[]
10. Skype	[]	[]

2) Extent to which you use social media is: (a) Daily [] (b) Weekly [] (c) 1-3 hours [] (d) 3-5 hours []
(e) Others-specify-----

3) My use of social media is for: (a) News generation [] (b) for academic purposes [] (c) For social interaction [] (d) for entertainment (e) others-specify-----

4) What other gratifications/satisfactions you gain from the social media: **specify please** -----

SECTION (B) RESPONDENTS BIO DATA

- 1) Sex: male [] female []
- 2) Age: 16 – 20 [] 20 – 25 [] 26 – 30 [] 30 - above []
- 3) Level: 100[] 200 [] 300 [] 400 []